

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OBODO-OBUNSELI****FIRST NAME: RACHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DGG****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian style (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 0%

The author used MSWord 2013 on Windows 11Pro

QUIZ: INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING (DOCTORATE)

1. Which of the following best defines plagiarism in academic research?
 - Copying and pasting content from the internet without a citation but modifying some words to avoid detection.
 - Citing all sources properly but using a significant portion of another scholar's work, even if permission is granted.
 - Using another person's ideas or words without proper attribution, including direct quotations, paraphrasing, or submitting someone else's work as your own.¹**
 - Collaborating with a colleague to review your paper for grammar and clarity before submission.

¹ Laurent Cleenwerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 34.

2. When is it generally unnecessary to provide a citation in academic writing?
- When summarising a scholar's argument in your own words, even if the idea is not yours.
 - When stating your original analysis, opinion, or interpretation.²**
 - When using a unique phrase or terminology coined by another researcher.
 - When presenting statistical data from a published study.
3. Turabian states that a well-structured research argument should have five essential elements. Which of the following best describes the role of a warrant in an argument?
- A warrant is the central claim of an argument, stating the main point the writer wants the reader to accept.
 - A warrant is the specific evidence to support a claim, such as data, citations, or examples.
 - A warrant is the reader's counterargument, representing objections or alternative perspectives that the writer must acknowledge.
 - A warrant is the logical connection between a claim and its supporting reason, explaining why the evidence justifies the claim.³**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 37.

³ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

4. According to Turabian, effective planning is essential for assembling a coherent research argument. Which of the following best describes the recommended approach to drafting a research paper?
- A rigid approach should be followed, where every element of the argument is pre-determined and must not be adjusted during the writing process.
 - A draft should be written without a structured plan, allowing ideas to develop spontaneously without concern for coherence.
 - Only data and immediately useful sources should be saved; irrelevant materials should be discarded permanently.
 - An open-minded approach should be taken, following a structured plan while remaining flexible to adapt and refine arguments as the writing progresses.⁴**
5. What is the fundamental guideline for spelling and punctuation in academic writing, as outlined by Turabian?
- Writers should adopt any spelling and punctuation style they prefer as long as it remains consistent throughout their work.
 - Writers should consistently follow the spelling and punctuation rules prescribed by their institution or discipline, using authoritative references like the Merriam-Webster Dictionary when in doubt.⁵**
 - Spelling and punctuation rules should be based on personal preference, with no requirement to follow institutional or disciplinary guidelines.

⁴ Turabian, 58.

⁵ Ibid., 302-303, 315-327.

- The best approach is to alternate between American and British spelling conventions to appeal to a broader audience.
6. Which of the following best reflects Turabian's guidelines on using abbreviations in academic writing?
- Abbreviations should be used liberally to make the text more concise and accessible to a broader audience.
- Abbreviations should be used sparingly to maintain formality, ensuring that the paper does not appear too technical or informal.⁶**
- Once an abbreviation is introduced, it should replace the entire term in every instance throughout the paper, regardless of context.
- There are no established rules for abbreviations; writers should use them according to their preferences.
7. In a bibliography, which of the following does not correctly represent the required citation information?
- Author(s), editor(s), title, publisher, year of publication, edition, and volume number.
- Editors, title, year of publication, and a URL for an online source.
- Author(s), year of publication, publisher, volume, page, and edition number.⁷**
- Translator(s), year of publication, title, publisher, and place of publication.

⁶ Turabian, 353-369.

⁷ Ibid., 148.

8. Which of the following best describes a key factor contributing to successful dissertation research, as outlined by Sampson Jr.?
- Relying solely on individual research efforts to avoid bias and maintain academic independence.
 - Following a structured approach incorporating good communication, planning, and effective writing processes.⁸**
 - Prioritizing methodological complexity over clarity to demonstrate high academic rigour.
 - Avoiding engagement with prior research to ensure complete originality in dissertation work.
9. According to the *English Style Guide* used by the European Commission, what is the recommended approach to spelling in British English, particularly in areas influenced by external factors?
- The guide strictly adheres to traditional British spelling without influence from other languages or disciplines.
 - British spelling should remain consistent, but specific terms, such as “program” in IT and “sulfur” in scientific contexts, have been adapted due to global influences.⁹**

⁸ James P Sampson, Jnr, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 13-15.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 17.

- British English spellings should be replaced with American ones when writing for an international audience.
- To ensure clarity, all British spellings should be phonetically adjusted to match standard pronunciation.

10. Which of the following best describes the rule for using abbreviations in formal writing as outlined in the *English Style Guide* for the European Commission?

- Abbreviations should always be used in place of full terms to reduce redundancy in writing.
- Abbreviations should be introduced by spelling out the full term first, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses, and a list of abbreviations should be included if multiple are used.**¹⁰
- Abbreviations should be avoided entirely unless they are universally recognised in all languages.
- Abbreviations can be created freely by shortening long words, even if they do not follow an established convention.

¹⁰ European Commission, 41–42.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. European Commission, 2021.

Sampson Jr, James P. *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.